

MYCOFLORA OF READY-TO-EAT “KATI” IN AKUNGBA METROPOLIS, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

This study on "Mycoflora in Ready-To-Eat “Kati” within Akungba Metropolis, Ondo state Nigeria", explored the fungi diversity associated with the traditional fermentation process of Kati, a locally produced cereal product from maize. Samples were collected from various markets in the Akungba metropolis, ensuring freshness and diverse sources. The study aimed at providing insights into the mycoflora composition of Kati, shedding light on potential beneficial or detrimental microorganisms involved in the fermentation process. The findings contributed to the understanding of the microbial ecology of Kati production which includes fungal genera such as *Aspergillus*, *Saccharomyces*, *Candida*, *Geotrichum*, *Fusarium* and *Penicillium*. This knowledge improves Kati's safety, quality, and overall processing. This research is crucial for the local community and broader scientific knowledge, addressing the importance of mycoflora in traditional food fermentation practices.

Keywords: Cereal, Kati, mycobiota, Ondo State, fermented food, food safety

INTRODUCTION

In sub-Saharan Africa, maize and sorghum stand out as the most widely consumed cereals, amenable to various processing techniques suitable for both adults and infants, as well as for individuals who are ill. (Ojokoh *et al.*, 2017). These cereals can undergo various processing methods, introducing diversity into the consumption of staple foods. Fermented cereals constitute a significant portion of dietary practices in numerous African nations. In developing countries, fermented foods are predominantly crafted in households, villages, and small-scale cottage industries, garnering widespread consumer acceptance. Examples of locally fermented cereal foods encompass ogi, burukutu, pito, masa, kunu-zaki, and agidi (Adegbehingbe, 2014; Achi and Ukwuru 2015).

The fermentation of staple foods functions as a crucial method for supplying a substantial source of nourishment to extensive rural populations. This plays a significant role in bolstering food security by expanding the array of raw materials applicable to the creation of edible products. The fermentation process augments the nutrient content of foods by facilitating the biosynthesis of vitamins, essential amino acids, and proteins, thereby enhancing protein quality and improving fiber digestibility. (Oyewole and Isah, 2012). Furthermore, it boosts the availability of micronutrients by breaking down anti-nutrient factors. Employing biological and natural methods to elevate the nutritional value of food items holds superior safety benefits compared to chemicals, as products synthesized through biotechnology are generally less

toxic (Adegbehingbe *et al.*, 2017).

Fermentation, acknowledged as one of the oldest, most prevalent, and cost-effective methods for food processing and preservation, serves as a protective measure against the proliferation of aflatoxin (Ajayi and Asunbo, 2019). In African countries, fermented cereals-based food products can be categorized either by the raw cereal ingredient employed in their preparation or by the texture of the fermented product. Classification based on raw cereal ingredients includes Wheat-based foods such as bouza and kishk; Rice-based food like buza; Maize-based foods including ogi (agidi) and kenkey; Millet-based food like kunuzaki; and Sorghum-based foods such as pito, bogobe, kiswa, burukutu, and injera (Ajayi and Asunbo, 2019).

Categorization based on food texture encompasses the following: Liquid (gruel) examples include ogi, mahewu, burukutu, pito, and uji. Solid (dough) and dumplings comprise kenkey and agidi, while Dry (bread) options include kiswa and injera. Maize serves as a primary food source in Africa and South America, surpassing its consumption in the developed world. The per capita cereal consumption was estimated to exceed 100kg annually. Recently, there has been an upswing in maize consumption, attributed to population growth. The introduction of advanced processing concepts and foreign food products, such as wheat bread, wheat-based or milk-based weaning foods, yogurt, and larger beer, to tropical countries led to a rapid surge in demand during the early post-independence period, as these products were associated with elevated status (Ajayi and Asunbo, 2019).

Kati, also known as Agidi, a traditional food product, is a gel-like substance ranging in color from cream to glossy. It is

typically crafted from maize (*Zea mays*), although millet and sorghum can also be utilized. The color of agidi is influenced by the specific substrates employed in its production; maize yields a creamy to glassy white hue, sorghum imparts a light brown color, and millet results in a grey to greenish shade. This food item has gained widespread popularity, earning acceptance across diverse multi-ethnic groups and socioeconomic classes. Particularly prevalent in southern Nigeria, agidi is enjoyed either on its own or paired with vegetable soup, stew, bean-cake ("akara"), or "moi-moi." Additionally, it serves as a weaning food for infants and a light meal, particularly suitable for post-operative patients (Idise, 2007).

Fresh and uncontaminated maize purchased from the market, approximately 250g in weight, was meticulously washed using clean water. The washed grains were submerged in water and left to ferment for three days. Afterward, the fermented grains were combined with clean sorghum leaves (oroporo) and wet-milled using clean water, undergoing an additional fermentation period of two hours. The resulting slurry was cooked without sieving at a temperature of 100°C for 10-15 minutes, with continuous stirring over heat. The partially cooked slurry was then shaped into a ball and wrapped in sterile cocoa leaves before being recooked for approximately 15 minutes in a pressure pot to produce 'egidi' or "kati" Figure 1 (Ogiehor *et al.*, 2005). The traditional method of processing Kati is that maize or sorghum grains are sorted and cleaned and then washed with clean water and soaked in clean water for 24-48 h. The water is drained off, wetly milled (using a commercial milling machine) and sieved (using clean muslin cloth). It is allowed to sediment (24 – 48 h, optional), and wet-sieved (using clean muslin cloth) before

being decanted, the ogi slurry is boiled and cooked at $78\pm 2.5^{\circ}\text{C}$ and the kati is produced.

Moreover, kati tends to deteriorate swiftly during storage, typically lasting only 2-3 days, necessitating the repetition of the laborious and time-consuming production cycles to maintain a consistent supply. These challenges underscore the necessity to develop methods that extend the shelf life while upholding economic, safety, nutritional, and overall quality standards, aiming to meet the escalating demand. This study was therefore conducted to assess the mycoflora load and safety status of agidi produced in the Akungba communities within the Akoko area of Ondo State.

2.0 Materials and Methodology

2.1 Sample Collection

The fermented cereal product, 'Kati,' was procured from distinct markets, specifically Ibaka, Okusa, and Ikare, all situated in Akoko, Ondo State. Strict attention was given to guarantee that the acquired samples were freshly prepared on the same day. Using aseptic procedures, the samples were carefully collected in clean polythene bags and promptly transported to the Laboratory (Microbiology Laboratory, AAUA) for further analysis. The selected samples encompassed both sweet and unsweetened varieties. The equipment used for this study was properly sterilized.

2.1.1 Media Preparation

The media used were Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA) and Sabouraud Dextrose Agar (SDA) respectively. 39g of PDA was weighed using a spatula, a piece of foil paper and a weighing balance. The media was poured inside a conical flask and was then dissolved in 1000ml of sterile distilled water. 65g of SDA was also weighed and

dissolved likewise in another conical flask. The mixture was homogenized by gently shaking it and the top of the flask was corked with cotton wool wrapped in a foil paper. This is to prevent the media from spilling off during autoclaving. The media were, autoclaved at a temperature of 121°C for 15 minutes. The autoclaved was then switched off and the steam was allowed to escape making sure that it cooled to 0°C before unpacking the few had been cooled, it was then carefully aseptically dispensed into the sterilized Petri-dishes. The media preparation was done according to the manufacturer's specifications.

2.1.2 Serial Dilution

1g of the freshly prepared Kati/Agidi sample (sweet and sour) was dissolved in a test tube containing 9ml of sterile distilled water, the dilution was thoroughly shaken to obtain a uniform suspension of microorganisms and diluted serially (Ajayi and Asunbo, 2019).

2.2 Isolation and Enumeration of Microorganisms

Microorganism isolation was carried out using the pour plate method. In each of the three sterile Petri dishes arranged on the swabbed workbench, 1ml of diluents 10^{-3} and 10^{-5} were dispensed. Subsequently, 20ml of PDA was gently swirled into two Petri dishes to ensure even microorganism distribution, and the same process was followed with 20ml of SDA in the other two Petri dishes. The plates were left to solidify and then incubated at 25°C for 3-5 days. After 72 hours, visible growth was observed, and the number of colonies per plate was counted and documented as Colony Forming Units (CFU). The obtained isolates underwent proper microbiological methods for identification

(Ajayi and Asunbo, 2019).

2.3 Identification of pure cultures

A drop of Lactophenol-in-cotton blue was placed on a clean grease-free slide, an inoculating needle was used to remove a piece of mycelium free from the fungal pure culture and placed on the stained slide, teasing it out using two pointed needles. A cover slip was carefully placed on it to avoid air bubbles, after which it was examined first under the low power (x10) and then under the high power (x40) objective lens of a light microscope. The structures seen were drawn and compared with the fungal structures found in a compendium (Ajayi and Asunbo, 2019).

3.0 Results

This study shows different types of fungal species isolated from 'kati' a fermented cereal. Twenty-four fungal species were isolated from the kati samples obtained for this study. This includes *Aspergillus flavus*, *Aspergillus clavatus*, *Aspergillus niger*, *Fusarium oxysporum*, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, *Geotrichum candidum*, *Candida lusitanae*, *Saccharomyces pombe*, and *Penicillium notatum*.

The mycoflora diversity varied across different Kati production sites, suggesting the influence of local environmental

factors and production practices. The Kati samples obtained from Okusa region had the highest mould occurrence, while the samples gotten from Ibaka and Ikare had the same mould occurrence as shown in Table 1

Additionally, both sweet and sour variants of Kati exhibited distinct fungal profiles. *Fusarium oxysporum*, *Geotrichum candidum*, *Candida lusitanae* and *Saccharomyces pombe* were isolated from the sweetened kati samples, while *Aspergillus flavus*, *Aspergillus clavatus*, *Aspergillus niger*, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* and *Penicillium notatum* were isolated from the unsweetened kati samples.

Table 1 presents the moulds associated with ready-to-eat Kati collected from different locations

Table 2 presents the morphological identification of the moulds associated with ready-to-eat Kati collected from different sources

Table 3 presents the microscopic identification of the moulds associated with ready-to-eat Kati collected from different sources

Table presents the frequency and percentage occurrence of the moulds associated with ready-to-eat Kati collected from different sources

Table 1: Moulds associated with ready-to-eat Kati collected from different locations

S/N	Mould	Location
1	<i>Fusarium oxysporum</i>	Ibaka
2	<i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i>	Ibaka
3	<i>Geotrichum candidum</i>	Ibaka
4	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	Ikare
5	<i>Penicillium notatum</i>	Ikare
6	<i>Aspergillus clavatus</i>	Ikare
7	<i>Saccharomyces pombe</i>	Okusa
8	<i>Candida lusitanae</i>	Okusa
9	<i>Aspergillus flavus</i>	Okusa
10	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	Okusa

Table 2: Morphological identification of the moulds associated with ready-to-eat Kati collected from different sources

S/N	Isolate code	Appearance of	N a t u r e o f	Spore Producing
1	A10-3 1	Floccose, Greyish rose	Septate (Hyaline)	Conidiophores
2	A10-3 2	Granular, Cream	Yeast	Yeast
3	A10-5	Powdery, White	Septate (Hyaline)	Conidiophores
4	B10-3 1	Powdery, Brown	Septate (Hyaline)	Conidiophores
5	B10-3 2	Velvety, Green	Septate (Hyaline)	Conidiophores
6	B10-5 1	Powdery, Green	Septate (Hyaline)	Conidiophores
7	C10-3 1	Smooth, Cream	Yeast	Yeast
8	C10-3 2	Smooth, White	Yeast	Yeast
9	C10-5	Velvety, Green	Septate (Hyaline)	Conidiophores

KEY

A = IBAKA A10-3 1, C10-3 2, C10-3 1, A10-3 2 = Sweetened samples
 B = IKARE B 10-3 1, B10-3 2, A10-5, B10-5, C10-5 = Unsweetened samples
 C = OKUSA

Table 3: Microscopic identification of the moulds associated with ready-to-eat Kati collected from different sources

S/N	Isolate code	Microgram Diagram	Identical Fungal Strain
1	A10-3 1		<i>F u s a r i u m oxysporum</i>
2	A10-3 2		<i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i>
3	A10-5		<i>Geotrichum candidum</i>
4	B10-3 1		<i>Aspergillus niger</i>
5	B10-3 2		<i>Penicillium notatum</i>
6	B10-5 1		<i>Aspergillus clavatus</i>
7	C10-3 1		<i>Saccharomyces pombe</i>
8	C10-3 2		<i>Candida lusitanae</i>
9	C10-5		<i>Aspergillus flavus</i>

Table 4: Frequency and Percentage Occurrence of Fungal Isolates obtained from the moulds associated with ready-to-eat Kati collected from different sources

Fungal Isolates	Frequency	Percentage Occurrence (%)
<i>Aspergillus</i>	3	33.33
<i>Saccharomyces</i>	2	22.22
<i>Geotichum</i>	1	11.11
<i>Candida</i>	1	11.11
<i>Fusarium</i>	1	11.11
<i>Penicillium</i>	1	11.11
Total	9	100

4.0 Discussion

The investigation of mycoflora in ready-to-eat "Kati" within Akungba Metropolis aimed to provide insights into the fungal composition of this popular street food in Akungba region, with potential implications for food safety and public health. The findings of this study contribute valuable information to the understanding of microbial contamination in Kati, particularly in a region where such analyses are limited.

Various fungal species that were aflatoxigenic in nature were isolated from this popular food source 'kati' being consumed in some Akoko communities in Nigeria. Occurrence of aflatoxigenic mould contamination in fermented cereal – 'kati' sample could pose threat to public health. Generally, moulds lead to great economic losses and constitute a major production of mycotoxins (Pandey et al., 2023).

The presence of various fungal species in the ready-to-eat "Kati" samples indicates the potential for contamination during handling, preparation, or storage. Several factors may contribute to the microflora diversity observed, including unhygienic practices during food processing, inadequate storage conditions, or the use of contaminated ingredients. Fungal contaminants identified in the study, such as *Aspergillus*, *Penicillium* and *Fusarium*, are known to be common spoilage organisms in food and are associated with mycotoxin production, which poses potential health risks to consumers (Pandey et al., 2023).

This study shows that *Aspergillus* spp was the most prevalent 33% followed by *Saccharomyces* 22%. Other isolated moulds were *Fusarium* spp, *Penicillium* spp., *Candida* and *Geotrichum* spp. (Table

3). *Aspergillus* spp is widely incriminated as contaminant of human foods (Afriyie-Gyawu et al., 2008), especially cereals. The presence of *Aspergillus* spp is not only of economic importance but also represents a real health hazard. They can have allergic, toxigenic and pathogenic effects through the production of mycotoxins (Atehnkenget al., 2008).

Isolated fungi like *Aspergillus* and *Fusarium* have been considered to be a major leading factor in food spoilage, resulting in great economic losses and constituting a public health hazard by producing varieties of mycotoxins causing food poisoning (Jeff-Agboola and Omosanyin, 2017; Ajayi and Asunbo, 2019). The identification of specific fungal species such as *Aspergillus* and *Fusarium* allows for a targeted assessment of the potential risks associated with mycotoxin production. Monitoring and controlling these contaminants are crucial to ensuring the safety of ready-to-eat foods like "Kati." Implementation of good hygiene practices, proper storage conditions, and regular quality checks can significantly reduce the risk of fungal contamination.

Food and Drug Administration (FDA) established regulatory working guidelines on the acceptable levels of aflatoxins in human foods set at 20ppb for total aflatoxins (Ajayi and Asunbo, 2019). The most effective means to prevent aflatoxigenic mould contamination of 'kati' is through the application of strict hygienic measures during the processing.

This study shows that the occurrence of relatively high levels of moulds and aflatoxigenic fungi in agidi samples analyzed presents high risk to consumers' health. It is therefore suggested that a statutory food regulating body dedicated to protecting public health and consumer

interest in the area of food safety and hygiene be established. And those in existence should be strengthened with appropriate resources. Its main function would be to take all reasonable steps to ensure that food products meets the high standards of food safety and food handlers should observe necessary food production regulations and ethics.

CONCLUSION

This investigation into the mycoflora in Kati production within Akungba Metropolis has provided valuable insights into the fungal diversity associated with this traditional food product. The study revealed a diverse range of fungi, including both beneficial and potentially undesirable species, present in Kati samples sourced from different markets. The identification and characterization of these fungal isolates contribute to our understanding of the microbial ecology of Kati production. Furthermore, the findings underscore the

importance of proper hygiene practices and quality control measures in the production of Kati. The presence of various fungal species highlights the need for meticulous attention to the production process, from raw material sourcing to final product packaging. This information is crucial for producers, regulatory bodies, and consumers alike in ensuring the safety and quality of Kati. In conclusion, the study sheds light on the mycoflora associated with Kati production, emphasizing the significance of implementing good manufacturing practices to mitigate potential health risks. Future research and interventions can build upon these findings to develop strategies for enhancing the safety and quality of Kati, contributing to the overall improvement of traditional food production practices in the region.

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